

LANGUAGE AS A SOCIAL PHENOMENON

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Abstract: Language is a phenomenon that plays an important role in human life. The whole life of a person is connected with language, and with the help of language, people have the opportunity to exchange ideas. At the same time, human language is a very complex phenomenon that embodies contradictory qualities.

Key words: language, phonetics, society, grammatical structure, linguistics, social nature

Any language consists of phonetic structure, grammatical structure and vocabulary. These components of the language are interconnected on the basis of certain laws and form a whole language, the language forms a coherent system on the basis of these compounds. Development of language, internal structure, the fact that language is a complex system I. A. Baudouin de Courtenay, H.B. Krushevsky, F.F. Fortunatov, V.A. Bogoroditsky, A.A. Potebnya, A.A. Shakhmatov, S.P. Obnorsky, V.V. Vinogradov, A.M. Peshkovsky, L.V. It is covered in the works of linguists such as Sherba. In terms of its internal structure, a language is a complex system consisting of a certain number of closely related language units and rules for using these units. The mutual differentiation of language and speech phenomena, the study of the nature of their relationship existed in Arabic linguistics as early as the VIII-IX centuries. The relationship form of these concepts has been attracting the attention of world linguists until now. Smernitsky A. I., Panfilov V.Z., Melnichuk A.S., Solnsov V.M. Prague linguists like But literally scientific-theoretical and practical differentiation of language and speech phenomena and their specific units; Giving a completely new meaning to the concepts of "language" and "speech" is related to the teaching created by F. de Saussure and his followers. Attitudes to language and speech issues are interpreted in a unique way in languages of a certain level of development of the world. In particular, despite the fact that some opinions are being expressed in the current Uzbek linguistics about the difference between language and speech phenomena, which are dialectically related to each other, there are many aspects of this issue that need to be resolved.

Language is the most important tool of communication in human society, and serves as the main tool that preserves all cultural and scientific wealth created in the course of the long historical development of mankind and transmits it from generation to generation. Important issues such as the nature, essence, and role of language in human society require scientific study.

In the history of the science of linguistics, there have been various theories and trends in the study of the most important issues such as the nature and social essence of language. A. Schleicher on the nature of language, biological nature of language, G. Paul on the fact that

language is only an individual phenomenon, Wundt on the relationship between folk psychology and language and wrote several works.

The signs of the language make it possible to distinguish it from other means of communication, to characterize the language as a social phenomenon. In general, language, as the most important means of personal communication, has been in close contact with society and all its members, who use language extensively and comprehensively in their culture, life and work. It is impossible to deeply understand the language system, its units and categories without determining the function of language in society and its relationship with society, human mind and thinking ability. People express their thoughts, desires, intuition and mental experiences in interaction, influence each other and understand each other. The fact that language serves as a communication tool in society is its communicative function. In addition, language performs an expressive and accumulative function.

Language arose out of the need to communicate with other people. The fact that this need is related to the changes that occur in people's spheres of society and human activity is reflected in the language, first of all, in the vocabulary of the language. Therefore, language is not a natural and biological phenomenon, the emergence and development of language does not obey the laws of nature.

The social nature of language requires its existence in society, not in individuals. Language is created by society, and its fate is closely related to the fate of society. Language is a social phenomenon. As a social phenomenon, it differs from natural phenomena. For example, natural-biological and physiological characteristics of people (eating, breathing, development, etc.) develop in accordance with the laws of nature, independently of society. But in order to speak and think in a language, there must be a community of people. Therefore, unlike natural phenomena, language is a social phenomenon created and served by the society of individuals.

It seems that language is a social phenomenon by its nature.

One of the main problems of the science of linguistics is the study of the internal structure of the language. Any language consists of phonetic structure, grammatical structure and vocabulary. These components of the language are interconnected on the basis of certain laws and form the whole language, the language forms a coherent system based on these compounds. In terms of its internal structure, a language is a complex system consisting of a certain number of closely related language units and rules for using these units. The laws of interaction and connection of the units that make up the language system are complex and multifaceted. Although the language is a whole system, this system consists of a combination of levels that have their own characteristics and are considered components of the language system. Each level has its own units and concepts, which differ from each other. For example, the phonetic-phonological level differs from the vocabulary level, and the vocabulary level differs from the grammatical level. However, these levels make up the whole language system in relation to each other. The main levels that make up the language system are:

Phonetic-phonological level.

Vocabulary level.

Grammatical level.

This level of language studies speech sounds in the language system. The words and sentences used for the exchange of ideas, of course, find their expression in the system of sounds. The sound system of the language can be studied from different angles, because

speech sounds are a complex phenomenon according to their nature and the function they perform in the language system. The sounds of human speech are a type of sounds that appear in nature according to their physical characteristics. Therefore, the study of the sound system is approached from the acoustic point of view. However, human sounds, unlike other sounds in nature, are the product of the speech organs controlled by the human nervous system. Therefore, sounds are also studied from a physiological point of view. Finally, sounds can be studied from the point of view of their function in language, because sounds do not exist in language by themselves. They play an important role in forming words and providing a means of communication. The science of phonetics studies the physical and biological properties of sounds. Phonology studies the functions of sounds in the language system. There are several aspects of phonetics: theoretical phonetics, applied phonetics, segmental, supramental phonetics and phonology.

Phonology, which is the fourth main branch of phonetics, is considered as a separate science.

Phonetics is inextricably linked with morphology and syntax, lexis and methodology, which are other parts and levels of language. Speech is phonetically divided into phrases, tacts, syllables and speech sounds. A phrase is the largest phonetic unit of speech, and it is bounded by a pause on both sides and has its own tone. Phrases are composed of tact. The sum of one or more syllables, located between two small pauses of a phrase and pronounced with a single accent, is called a tact. A phrase has as many accents as there is a tact.

Tact consists of syllables. A syllable is a phonetic unit made up of one or more sounds and pronounced with one stroke. There are several theories related to the definition of a syllable. Two of them: phonological syllable theory and phonetic syllable theory are widespread. When studied as a unit of phonetics, sounds are called "speech sounds" or "backgrounds". "Background" is a common term in modern linguistics, and it is the smallest, non-meaningful unit of speech.

One of the aspects in the study of speech sounds is called phonology. Phonology studies the functional value of speech sounds. The source of learning phonology is phoneme. A phoneme is the smallest, indivisible language unit that makes up words, word forms and morphemes and serves to distinguish meaning. For example, tup-tup; put down; sut-sud words are distinguished by phonemes. Words that differ by only one phoneme are called quasi-onyms. All phonemes in the language are in a certain range relative to each other. The connection and interaction of phonemes constitutes a phonological system.

Vocabulary level

The vocabulary level of the language consists of the sum of the words that exist in the language. The vocabulary level is different from the phonetic-phonological and grammatical levels of the language as it is always changing and developing. The process of development of science, technology, and culture requires the constant change of the vocabulary level. Accordingly, the vocabulary level of the language consists of several layers that differ from each other in terms of the scope of their appearance and use. People express objects and events with the help of the word, which is considered the main unit of the vocabulary level; and in a sentence, words combine together to create an opportunity to express an idea. Lexicology studies the vocabulary level. Definition of a word, word and object, word and concept, changes in vocabulary, relationship between words, layers of vocabulary are the main issues studied by lexicology. Changes in the initial meaning and form of words are

studied by etymology, the dictionary and its structure by lexicography, the meaning of the word and its development by semasiology. Phraseologisms are studied in connection with lexicology.

The vocabulary of the language can be studied from several points of view. From the point of view of history, the vocabulary layer of the language can be divided into original and borrowed words. In every language, along with the words of its own layer, there are words of the assimilated layer, which is explained by the position of the language, the socio-historical process, and the influence of various relations between peoples and languages. A certain part of the vocabulary layer consists of dialect words. Dialect words serve as the main means of communication. Dialect words have a special place in enriching the vocabulary of the literary language. The vocabulary of the language is also different from the point of view of the level of consumption. In this respect, active and rarely used words differ. We will discuss this in detail below in "Linguistics and its departments" (in the example of the Uzbek language). The main source of increasing the vocabulary of a language is word creation, borrowing words from dialects, changes in the development of the meaning of the word, and transfer of meaning.

Grammatical level

The grammatical level of each language consists of the grammatical form of words, phrases and sentences. Grammar, like other levels of language, has its own units. The smallest grammatical unit is a morpheme, words are formed from morphemes, and words, in turn, participate in the construction of phrases and sentences. A sentence is a large and independent unit of grammar. There are also larger units than a sentence: complex syntactic (unit) whole, paragraph and text.

The grammatical structure of the language has its own characteristics.

First, the grammatical structure of the language: the structure of the word, rules of inflection and type, word combinations and types of grammar change very slowly as a product of historical development.

Second, grammar is generalizable. For example, words such as cart, higher education, stone, child have their own lexical meaning, but from a grammatical point of view, these words express the concept of objectivity and form a noun group. These words are summarized not by their lexical meaning, but by their grammatical meaning. Morphology and syntax study the grammatical structure of the language. Morphology examines word groups and their grammatical forms. Syntax studies the grammatical structure of speech. In this case, the word is the main unit. Units larger than sentences are also studied in syntax.

The language system consists of language units - phoneme, morpheme, word, sentence and a whole of language levels. It can be seen from the above that the phonetic, lexical, and grammatical aspects of the language, which is a means of communication, is a system that forms a mutual balance based on certain internal laws. The proportionality that makes up the system is manifested in specific rules. Sentences in a certain language are made up of words, words are made up of syllables, and syllables are made up of speech sounds. In other words, the words that make up the sentence are combined based on the rules of the language. Any combination of words cannot be a sentence. Words collected in a disorderly picture do not serve to express content. The sequence of words must be in accordance with a certain order and general rule. This situation itself shows that the language is a system. Sounds specific to a certain language make up the phonetic system of that language, the lexical system of words. A word adopted from one language to another is subject to the phonetic system and

pronunciation standards of that language. For example: some words that entered the Uzbek language from the Russian language adapt to Uzbek pronunciation standards: teapot-teapot, podnos-patnis. On the contrary, the words adopted from the Uzbek language to the Russian language are subject to the pronunciation standards of the Russian language: karovul-karaul, caravan-caravan, bazar-bazar.

In general, in a language, sounds, vocabulary, grammatical order are united and form a whole as a system. The levels that make up the language system mutually require each other. The connection between them is based on the general rules and laws of the language.

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